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Research Article

**COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN HERNIORRHAPHY
ALONE VERSUS HERNIOPLASTY IN SMALL-SIZED
PARAUMBILICAL HERNIA AT ALLIED HOSPITAL
FAISLABAD**

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Abstract:

Background- One of the common diseases is the paraumbilical hernia and throughout the world it is one of the most common disease who surgery is performed. Herniorrhaphy and hernioplasty are the significant surgery techniques and there is significant difference in both of these techniques.

Methods- In this study two groups were made, and each group had 50 subjects. This study was conducted to compare the difference in both surgery techniques that is herniorrhaphy and hernioplasty as it was a prospective randomized controlled trial. This comparison was done in paraumbilical hernia with complications in local wound for example total cost, operation time, recurrence rate and seroma.

Results- Result showed that in both techniques there was not a lot of difference in wound complications and hernia recurrence. Whereas total cost, time of operation and incision size was significantly reduced in herniorrhaphy.

Conclusion- It was concluded in this study that in the paraumbilical hernia the techniques of herniorrhaphy is better as compared to the hernioplasty as total cost, time of operation and incision size was significantly reduced in herniorrhaphy.

Keywords: Hernioplasty, Herniorrhaphy, paraumbilical

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the common diseases is the paraumbilical hernia among anterior abdominal and 85% of abdominal wall hernias is made up by this. This disease is common in adults and in children it is rarely found. Mesh repair and stature are important repairing techniques for paraumbilical hernia. These both techniques have various sub techniques. Throughout the world it is one of the most common disease whose surgery is performed.

Herniorrhaphy and hernioplasty are the significant surgery techniques and there is significant difference in both techniques. The significance of a techniques can be measured by the variants of recurrence of hernia. There are a lot of factors which are responsible for the recurrence of hernia after its surgery. However, the major causes are surgical site infection and larger seroma for recurrence. Moreover, by malnutrition, mellitus, diabetes, obesity, old age and drug addiction increase the chances for the surgical site infection.

Objective:

The aim of this study is to compare the results of both Herniorrhaphy and hernioplasty in paraumbilical hernia

METHODS:

This study was conducted in Allied Hospital Faisalabad. In this study two groups were made, and each group had 50 subjects.

First Group: Included random 50 people with to paraumbilical herniorrhaphy

Second Group: Included 50 people randomly with mesh insertion to paraumbilical hernioplasty This

study was conducted to compare the difference in both surgery techniques that is herniorrhaphy and hernioplasty as it was a prospective randomized controlled trial. This comparison was done in paraumbilical hernia with complications in local wound for example total cost, operation time, recurrence rate and seroma.

Exclusion and Inclusion Criteria:

In this the exclusion criteria were having the defect more than 3cm or recurrent paraumbilical hernias while inclusion criteria was people having the age between 21 to 55 years and had defect less than 3cm and uncomplicated paraumbilical hernia

Laboratory assessment:

Liver function tests, blood sugar, and complete blood count was observed.

Clinical assessment:

Patients of both groups were tested for the medical diseases like heart diseases, pulmonary, renal, hypertension and diabetes etc.

Ultra-sound of Abdominal:

In this the abdominal size was determined with wall defect size, associated pathology and hernia content.

Statistical Analysis:

For statistical analysis SPSS version 20 was used

RESULTS:

In group one 62% were females and 38% were males while in group two 55% were females and 45% were males. Both groups include people having the age between 21 to 55 years.

Table 1. Demographics of both groups

		Group statistics				t test	P value
		Hernioplasty (n=50)		Herniorrhaphy (n=50)			
Age (in years)	Mean±SD	43.34±7.70		42.60±8.17		0.466	0.642
	Range	27-55		27-55			
	Mean differences	0.740					
		No.	%	No.	%	X ²	
Sex	Male	19	38	23	46	1.67	0.48
	Female	31	62	27	54		

Result showed that in both techniques there was not a lot of difference in wound complications and hernia recurrence. Whereas total cost, time of operation and incision size was significantly reduced in herniorrhaphy.

Table 2. Both groups' operative details

Operative details		Hernioplasty (n=50)	Herniorrhaphy (n=50)	P value
Drain insertion		50	33	<0.001*
Incision size (cm)	Mean±SD	10.47±1.33	8.38±0.92	<0.001*
	Range	8-14	6.90-10.40	
	Mean differences	2.092		
Time of operation (min)	Mean±SD	40.06±3.26	30.20±3.15	<0.001*
	Range	32-45	25-40	
	Mean differences	9.860		
Overall cost (LE)	Mean± SD	1712±284.38	1419±154.49	<0.001*
	Range	1200-2400	1200-2200	
	Mean differences	293.000		

Table 3. Recurrence rate comparison

Recurrence rates	Group statistics						X ²	P value	
	Hernioplasty (n=50)		Herniorrhaphy (n=50)		Total (n=100)				
	N	%	N	%	N	%			
3rd month	No	50	100.00	50	100.00	100	100.00	0.00	1.000 ^{NS}
	Yes	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00		
6th month	No	50	100.00	49	98.00	99	99.00	1.01	0.315 ^{NS}
	Yes	0	0.00	1	2.00	1	1.00		

DISCUSSION:

One of the common diseases is the paraumbilical hernia among anterior abdominal and 85% of abdominal wall hernias is made up by this. Herniorrhaphy and hernioplasty are the significant surgery techniques and there is significant difference in both techniques. The significance of a techniques can be measured by the variants of recurrence of hernia. There are a lot of factors which are responsible for the recurrence of hernia after its surgery. However, the major causes are surgical site infection and larger seroma for recurrence. Moreover, by malnutrition, mellitus, diabetes, obesity, old age and drug addiction increase the chances for the surgical site infection.

In this study two groups were made, and each group had 50 subjects. One had random 50 people with to paraumbilical herniorrhaphy. On the other hand, second had 50 people randomly with mesh insertion to paraumbilical hernioplasty

Concerning size and by and large budgetary cost, our outcomes demonstrated a noteworthy contrast between the two gatherings; the mean of entry point size in hernioplasty bunch was 10.47±1.33 cm. while in gathering (2) it was just 8.38±0.92 cm. Generally speaking, expenses were significantly reduced in second group as in 1st group it was 1712±284.38 Egyptian Pounds and second group 1419±154.49 Egyptian Pounds.

As to confusions, our information demonstrated that the requirement for addition of channel was altogether decreased among herniorrhaphy gathering (66%) than in hernioplasty gathering (100%), with p<0.001, just as wound contamination

which happened in four cases in hernioplasty gathering (8%) contrasted and one instance of twisted disease in herniorrhaphy gathering (2%).

CONCLUSION:

It was concluded in this study that in the paraumbilical hernia the techniques of herniorrhaphy is better as compared to the hernioplasty as total cost, time of operation and incision size was significantly reduced in herniorrhaphy.

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